

ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN INTERFACE AND DAMAGE IN GLASS FIBRE / THERMOSET MATRIX COMPOSITE MATERIALS AS A FUNCTION OF THE LOADING MODE

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ABSTRACT

Composites, bi-phasic materials made up of a fibre reinforced organic matrix, have very attractive mechanical and physical assets. If it is customary to analyse the composites behaviour as a function of their basic components, reinforcement and resin, the scientific and technical literature is much more discreet about the influence of the third parameter: the interface.

Indeed, the notion of interface is still quite blurred, and its analysis and modelisation remain complicated. Moreover softwares for micromechanical calculation and prediction of behaviours are mostly satisfied with the assumption of a perfect bond between fibre and matrix. Such a hypothesis is to be debated when one imagines the whole set of defects which can result from badly mastered adhesion mechanisms within a complicated technological context with 15 μm diameter filaments.

Therefore in order to quantify the influence of the interface on the damage of glass fibre/thermoset matrix materials, composite plates and pipes presenting interfaces of different qualities were subjected to various sollicitation types:

- monoaxial tension,
- interlaminar shear,
- biaxial tension,
- crack initiation and crack growth in opening mode.

The occurrence of first damage was noticed either from discontinuities appearing on the behaviour patterns (load-displacement curves) or by a monitoring of acoustic emissions. Fractographical observations of the composites under Scanning Electron Microscopy made it possible to complete the analysis in terms of damage mechanisms.

Very important differences were noticed in the behaviours, sometimes exceeding 50%. They confirm the incidence of the interface, which is often a preferential way for crack propagation.

Keywords : interface, damage, monoaxial loading, biaxial loading

1. STATE OF THE ART IN THE FIELD OF FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACE

Tests carried out on single-fibre composites (pull-out, fragmentation, compression, microindentation) /1/ make it possible to reach the fibre/matrix adhesion locally through interfacial shear stress measurement and to establish the basic features of stress transfer and interfacial failure. Some correlations were drawn between the values of single-filament tests and the interlaminar shear strengths of composite materials. Nevertheless, reliance on single-fibre measurements should be avoided for the prediction of composite properties. It is clear that none of these techniques offers a

complete and unambiguous method for measuring the interfacial shear strength between fibre and matrix /2/ (preponderating influence of a lot of experimental and human parameters).

Mechanical and thermomechanical macroscopic properties /3,4/ of composites strongly depend on the interface not only for matrix governed properties (in transverse tension for instance) but also for fibre governed ones (in longitudinal tension for example). This dependence occurs however through complex mechanisms and composite's responses to an action on the interface are often contradictory. As a consequence, optimisation of fibre/matrix interface and of interactions between reinforcement and resin for a given fibre/matrix couple should occur through a great set of mechanical tests.

In the present state of things, there are neither standards nor well established industrial methods about characterization of fibre/matrix interface. Nevertheless, some studies are being carried out in certain institutes. They should lead finally to the development of industrial characterization methods of the quality of the interface.

As an example we are going to present some results obtained in our laboratory on structures of different geometries and under monodirectional as well as bidirectional loading modes:

- flat pieces under monoaxial loading,
- tubing systems under internal pressure.

The different glass/epoxy and glass/polyester composite materials differ only by the nature of their sizing, all the specimens having the same thermal and thermomechanical history, hence the same structural state.

2. EXPERIMENTALS

2.1. Methods of characterization of the plates

2.1.1. Tensile and interlaminar shear tests

Tensile tests were carried out on a ZWICK 1474 dynamometer equipped with an extensometer, at a rate of 1 mm/min on 270x25x3 mm³ flat test pieces. Acoustic emission acquisition device comprises a piezoelectric sensor, a preamplifier and a data acquisition unit LOCAN AT (Physical Acoustic Corporation). The stress and the number of cumulated counts of acoustic emission versus strain are recorded simultaneously. Interlaminar shear tests were carried out following NFT 57104 standard (Short Beam Shear Test) on an INSTRON 1185 machine at a rate of 1 mm/min.

2.1.2. Mode I fracture mechanics

Linear elastic fracture mechanics enables the determination of an intrinsic characteristic of the composite material, which represents its crack growth resistance. This theory assumes the existence of a planar crack of a given size. A test of characterization of the interface was adapted in order to meet this condition. We have chosen a tension opening test (Mode I) in which a planar crack is propagating under a loading normal to this plane.

Fracture mechanics theory states that crack growth can occur if the surface energy required to extend an existing crack can just be delivered by the system. This energy is characterized by G , the strain energy release rate (available elastic energy), which is calculated from the compliance C ($C=\delta/P$), the specimen width B , the initial crack length a and the applied load P (δ =deflection):

$$G = P^2/2B \cdot dC/da \quad (1)$$

A critical strain energy release rate G_{Ic} is determined at crack initiation. However the fracture energy grows during crack propagation. This increase of G is described by the resistance curves, called R-curves, which are the plot of instantaneous G values as a function of crack extension Δa and leads to the determination of the propagation energy G_{Ip} . Analysis procedures and data reduction schemes are given in references /5,6/.

Mode I energy release rate G_I of the composite materials was measured by the double cantilever beam (DCB) technique. The specimens were rectangular beams cut from unidirectional laminates with fibers in the longitudinal direction of the specimens. Cracks were formed by a Tedlar® film (25µm thick) embedded in the mid-plane of the laminate. End tabs were bonded to the two half-

beams on the opposite sides of the crack. Geometry, fabrication procedures and preparation of the test specimens are given in reference /5/. The tests were carried out on an INSTRON 1115 machine at a rate of 2mm/min. Monitoring of acoustic emission allows the detection of crack initiation. The load P and the count rate were recorded versus deflection δ .

2.2. Methods of characterization of the tubes /7/

The tubes tested under internal pressure had a diameter of 100 mm and a total length of 1200 mm. A watertight assembly was designed so as to permit pressurisation of the test specimens. This consisted of conical metal connectors placed inside each extremity of the tube. The different pressure laws which can be applied are:

- * increasing pressure as a function of time (monotonic loading),
- * cyclic pressure with steps (repeated progressive loading) (UEWS test: see figure 1),
- * repeated sinusoidal pressure (dynamic fatigue),
- * constant pressure (creep).

Figure 1: Cycling loading in U.E.W.S. test

All of the pressure testing devices were designed at the Polymers and Composites Technology Laboratory of the Ecole des Mines de Douai (France) /8/.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Monoaxial mechanical behaviour of composite plates as a function of interface quality

3.1.1. Tensile and interlaminar shear strength.

The results were obtained on glass fabric / polyester resin composites (referenced 1 to 5), presenting nearly the same structure but different interface qualities. Whatever property is considered (tensile or interlaminar shear strength), the variations which are noted fall within standard deviation or remain low, and do not allow a significant discrimination of interfaces of different qualities.

Nevertheless, more sensitive damage analysis techniques, such as acoustic emission, make it possible to distinguish behaviours, for instance if the rise of the curve of acoustic emission cumulated counts vs. strain is taken as damage criterion (figures 2 and 3). These results were confirmed for unidirectional glass/epoxy composites, loaded in transverse tension, for which variation of 30% were observed.

Figure 2: Definition of the acoustic damage criterion

Figure 3: Critical strain (acoustic criterion)

3.1.2. Mode I fracture mechanics

R-curves - which give the evolution of the strain energy release rate as a function of crack extension - were plotted for 4 unidirectional glass/epoxy materials 1-2-3-4 with different interfaces. It appears that crack initiation (figure 5) and crack propagation (figure 4) energies can be affected by the interface quality up to 50%. Moreover it should be noticed that behaviours in initiation and in propagation are different. For instance crack initiation is difficult for the material 1, but after that, crack propagation occurs more easily [9].

Figure 4: Crack propagation energies

Figure 5: Crack initiation energies

From these first results on standard flat test pieces, one can remark that mode I fracture mechanics could be considered as a representative method of qualification and quantification of the fibre/matrix adhesion. Tension and interlaminar shear tests, although widely used, are less sensitive techniques, except if precise methods of damage analysis such as acoustic emission are used. Furthermore these conclusions are confirmed by the few results which can be found in international literature.

3.2. Biaxial mechanical behaviour of composite pipes as a function of interface quality

Beyond an incidence under monoaxial loading modes we have also shown the influence of the interface quality for more complex sollicitations and in particular for biaxial loading /7/.

Behaviour patterns have been measured as a function of interface quality under different internal pressure loading laws:

- * monotonic loading,
- * repeated progressive loading,
- * dynamic fatigue,
- * creep.

The tests related to four materials differing in the nature of the coupling agent with the same yarn count 1200 tex:

- * Ref. A: epoxy specific, direct roving, base 17 microns,
- * Ref. B: epoxy specific, direct roving, base 17 microns, (other supplier than for A)
- * Ref. C: polyvalent, direct roving,
- * Ref. D: assembled roving, same coupling agent as B, base 14 microns.

3.2.1. Monotonic behaviour

The patterns of behaviour gave curves with the following shapes (figure 6). According to the two criteria of damage used:

- * weeping, which is an industrial criterion, characterizing a certain crack propagation rate sufficient to allow the diffusion of the water through the wall,
- * limit of linearity, characterizing the first macroscopical damage, and which is a crack initiation criterion.

Figure 6: Instantaneous behaviour patterns (Curves left to right: Axial deformation; deformation perpendicular to the fibres; deformation parallel to the fibres; circumferential deformation)

The resistances measured on the four materials are given in relative value to the limit of linearity of material C, in table I.

Table I: Relative values of resistances under monotonic and cyclic pressures

Ref.	σ weeping	σ limit of linearity	σ U.E.W.S.	Durability: N cycles at ($P \rightarrow > 10^6$ cycles)
A	165	144	110	9,4 x
B	228	145	114	30,8 x
C	183	100	81	x
D	213	130	103	8,4 x

3.2..2. U.E.W.S.

The tests with progressive repeated loadings made it possible to get an accurate determination of the linear / non-linear transition of the materials. For each cycle, the values of pressures and axial deformations are registered. This procedure is continued until the strain at the tenth cycle, for a given pressure level, is no longer equal to that of the first one. At this point, the curve $P=f(\epsilon)$ is no longer linear and the corresponding circumferential stress is the ultimate elastic wall stress (U.E.W.S.) defined by Schwenke and Steveninck. The U.E.W.S. stress values are reported in table I. These are relative values to the stress at the limit of linearity of material C under monotonic loading. The classification between the different materials squares with those obtained for instantaneous tests at the limit of linearity, which offers the same damage mechanisms by crack initiation.

3.2.3. Fatigue

The fatigue behaviour of material B is represented by a Wöhler curve giving the evolution of the number of cycles to failure as a function of pressure. The average classification between the different materials in terms of relative number of cycles to failure for the same stress level (corresponding to the weeping pressure of material C) is given in table I.

3.2.4. Comparison of creep and fatigue

The curves of durability in fatigue and creep for material B are given in figure 8. The ratio of the slopes is about 2, which implies a long-term dynamic resistance which is greatly inferior to the static resistance. Also noteworthy is the position of the limit of linearity and of the threshold of U.E.W.S., in the vicinity of the long-term static resistance.

Figure 8 : Curves showing durability under cyclic and constant pressures

3.2.5. Damage mechanisms

The results show the influence of the interface on the mechanical properties and on the behaviour of tubular structures in glass/epoxy composites subjected to internal pressure. The level of

sensitivity to the interface quality is dependent on the type of load applied and the end of life criteria selected, weeping or threshold of non-linearity. Under monotonic loading one can observe maximum divergences of 17% on the values of weeping pressures; these gaps increase considerably if first damage pressures are considered, and can reach 30%. In terms of circumferential stresses (table 1), these differences are still more pronounced and can go as high as 25% for weeping stresses and 45% for limit of linearity. The fatigue lifetime is also very strongly affected by the nature of the fibre/matrix interface, which can make it possible to multiply the lifetime by 30.

The mechanical damage of glass/epoxy tubular structures submitted to internal pressure results from the initiation of cracks, followed by their propagation through the wall thickness. This is the cause of non-linearity in behaviour patterns and finally of weeping, which show up in the appearance of droplets of water on the outer surface of the tube. The participation of the interface in these damage mechanisms is shown up by the presence of transverse and longitudinal cracks, which appear on micrographs (figure 9). The analysis of their progression makes it possible to associate their origin with fibre/matrix adhesion. Indeed at high magnification we note that cracks result from interfacial debonding (figure 10).

Figure 9: Transverse and longitudinal cracks

Figure 10: Debonding at glass fibre/matrix interface

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, these results show the great influence of the interface on the mechanical behaviour of composite materials. Moreover they could allow the emergence of certain industrial characterization methods of the quality of the interfacial zone, although these methods still remain quite complex in their use and the damage mechanisms that they involve. The achievement of their development and of their validation should nevertheless be possible in the near future on the following condition: it requires some research endeavours, involving a close collaboration between manufacturers, fibre and sizing producers and laboratories in order to take into account the chemical nature of the components, the mechanisms of adhesion and the technological parameters /10/.

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